

CE21016 Cruise Report Summary

SyMonS_MoM_2 – Systematic Monitoring Survey of the Moira Mound Chain 2

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The Belgica Mound Province (BMP) in the NE Atlantic is home to diverse benthic megafauna, most notably cold water corals reefs. The reefs form mounds, which range in size from 3 to 12 m in height and occur in water depths of down to 1100m. In 2020, 7 benthic lander systems were deployed during the CE20011 cruise, to access the environmental controls on their growth and distribution patterns in the area. Each lander measured current speed and direction, temperature, biofouling and trapped current suspended particles for a period of 319 days. Cruise CE21011 sought out to recover, refit and redeploy these landers. Utilizing the *RV Celtic Explorer* and *Holland 1 ROV*, 6 of 7 landers were successfully recovered. 5 of the 6 landers had fallen over during their deployment cycle. Recovered ADCP data from these fallen landers show that 1 fell over before starting to record (02/10/2020), 3 fell over after 3.5 weeks and 1 fell over after 22 weeks. 1 of the 7 landers deployed last year in the Macnas Mounds region was not recovered and was missing from the site. Sediment trap data shows little deposition across the sites, despite a prolonged capture window (15 days). ADCP data from each of the sites show periodic fluxes across temperature and current speeds. Biofouling was present on each lander. Coral dominated sediment waves from the midslope region discovered last year were imaged using the downward-facing 1080i HD video camera. 2 landers were redeployed in the downslope area, after a site suitability evaluation. These landers will extend the current assessment of the reefs to a two-year record. This data will be useful for a number of projects including: the H2020 project "Integrated Assessment of Atlantic Marine Ecosystems in Space & Time" (*iATLANTIC*), the SFI-, GSI- and MI-funded "Mapping, Modelling and Monitoring Key Processes and Controls on Cold Water Coral Habitats in Submarine Canyons" (MMMonKey_Pro) programme, the Marine Protected Areas Monitoring and Management project funded through the INTERREG Va Regional Development Fund via SEUPG and the Marine Institute Post-doctoral Fellowship project, 'Mop_Up'/'Plast_Chem_Cora' (www.marinegeology.ucc.ie).